

Delivery of sustainable supply of non-food biomass to support a
“resource-efficient” Bioeconomy in Europe

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**Atlas with regional cost supply biomass potentials
for EU 28, Western Balkan Countries, Moldavia,
Turkey and Ukraine**

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About S2Biom project

The S2Biom project - Delivery of sustainable supply of non-food biomass to support a “resource-efficient” Bioeconomy in Europe - supports the sustainable delivery of non-food biomass feedstock at local, regional and pan European level through developing strategies, and roadmaps that will be informed by a “computerized and easy to use” toolset (and respective databases) with updated harmonized datasets at local, regional, national and pan European level for EU28, Western Balkans, Moldova, Turkey and Ukraine. Further information about the project and the partners involved are available under www.s2biom.eu.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

ABC	Activity Based Costing
BP	Base potential
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CAPRI	Common Agricultural Policy Regionalised Impact model.
CEEC	Central and Eastern European Countries
EFISCEN	European Forest Information SCENario model See glossary of models
EFSOS	European Forest Sector Outlook Study
EPIC	EPIC (Environmental Policy Integrated Climate Model)
EU	European Union
FADN	Farm Accountancy Data Network
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
FAOSTAT	Statistical service of FAO
FAWS	Forest available for wood supply
FYROM	Former Yugoslavian Republic of Macedonia
HNV	High Nature Value
HP	High potential
ILUC	Indirect land use change
MDF	Medium-density fibreboard
NPV	Net Present Value
NUTS	Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics of the European Union
NUTS0, NUTS1, NUTS2, NUTS3	NUTS, the Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics of the European Union structures the territorial units hierarchical, starting with the National level (= NUTS0), followed by NUTS1 and NUTS2 and NUTS3.
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OSB	Oriented strandboard
PCW	Post-consumer wood
RED	Renewable Energy Directive (EC, 2009)
SFR	Secondary forest residues
SOC	Soil Organic Carbon
SRC	Short rotation coppice
TP	Technical potential
UK	United Kingdom
UP / UDP	User defined potential
VAT	Value-added tax
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope and objectives of this report

Within the S2BIOM project, WP1 provides state of the art data on current and future sustainable lignocellulosic biomass cost and supply levels for EU28, Western Balkans, Ukraine, Turkey and Moldova.

This report provides an overview on the major results in form of maps, tables together with a brief explanation and interpretation. It complements the biomass supply tool¹ that allows interested parties to prepare their own customised tables, maps and cost-supply curves meeting their specific interests and requirements.

Potentials can be presented differing options in maps. An explanation on this issue is provided in Annex A7.

This report is based on the S2BIOM final data set that is described in S2BIOM report D1.5 (Datta et al. 2017) whereas the methods and data sets used to compile these data are described in S2BIOM report D1.6 (Dees et al. 2017).

The geographic scope, the spatial resolution and the thematic scope can be briefly described as follows.

Geographic scope:

- EU 28
- The Non- EU28 Western Balkans countries Montenegro, Macedonia (FYROM), Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Serbia, Kosovo.
- Turkey, Moldova Ukraine

Spatial resolution:

- EU 28 – NUTS 3
- Other countries – equivalently defined administrative units

Main categories covered:

- Forestry – Wood production and primary forest residues (10 subcategories)
- Agriculture - Primary production of lignocellulosic biomass crops and primary agricultural residues (20 subcategories)
- Grassland - Unused grassland cuttings (1 category)
- Other land use – biomass from landscape maintenance & road side verges (4 categories)
- Secondary residues from wood industries (8 categories)
- Secondary residues of industry utilising agricultural products (4 categories)
- Wastes (4 categories)

¹ <http://biomass-tools.eu>

2 Biomass atlas

2.1 Dedicated biomass crops and primary residues from agriculture

An overview of the biomass categories covered for the agricultural sector are listed in Table 1. There are five types of perennial crops covered and three types of short rotation coppices for which trial and plantation experience is wide spread in Europe. For residues all straw and stubbles from cereals and most common rotational arable crops in Europe are included. The same applies for the woody residues from the most common and spatially significant permanent crops in Europe for which five categories are distinguished.

Table 1 Subcategories of first level category 1 “Agriculture”

Second level subcategories		Third level subcategories		Final level subcategories			
ID	Name	ID	Name	ID	Name		
				2112	Miscanthus (Perennial grass)		
				2113	Switchgrass (Perennial grass)		
				2114	Giant reed (Perennial grass)		
				2115	Cardoon (Perennial crop)		
				2116	Reed Canary Grass (Perennial grass)		
		212	Short rotation coppice (SRC)	2121	SRC Willow		
				2122	SRC Poplar		
				2123	SRC Eucalyptus		
				2211	Rice straw		
				2212	Cereals straw		
				2213	Oil seed rape straw		
22	Primary residues from agriculture	221	Straw/stubbles	2214	Maize stover		
				2215	Sugarbeet leaves		
				2216	Sunflower straw		
				222	Woody pruning & orchards residues	2221	Residues from vineyards
						2222	Residues from fruit tree plantations (apples, pears and soft fruit)
						2223	Residues from olives tree plantations
		2224	Residues from citrus tree plantations				
		2225	Residues from nuts plantations				
		23	Unused grassland cuttings	231	Unused grassland cuttings	2311	Unused grassland cuttings (abandoned grassland, managed grasslands not used for feed)

In the following, the estimated potential supply and its cost are presented in the form of graphs, maps and tables following the definitions of the potentials as specified in the methods report D1.6 comprising of technical, base and user defined potentials. The potentials quantified in this Atlas refer mostly to the base potentials, which can be defined as the sustainable technical potential, considering agreed sustainability standards in:

- 1) CAP (Common Agricultural Policy) for agricultural farming practices which include applying conservation of Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) (basically part of Cross Compliance issues of ‘maintaining agricultural land in good farming and management condition’) and avoiding soil erosion and Greening.

- 2) Legal restrictions for protected areas and sustainability restrictions from current legislation.
- 3) Further restrictions resulting from RED (Renewable Energy Directive) sustainability criteria including conservation of land of high biodiversity value, high carbon stock, avoidance of direct land cover changes, avoidance of indirect land use changes, avoidance of competition with food & feed production, and avoid negative impacts on soils and water resources.

In addition to the base potential cost supply data are also presented for the Technical potential and for User Defined potentials. See Table 2 how the different potentials are defined per biomass type.

Table 2 Overview of agricultural biomass potential types and considerations

	Area/ Basis	Yield, Growth	Technical & environmental constraints on the biomass retrieval (per area)	Consideration of competing use	Mobilisation
Technical (dedicated biomass crops)	All good and low productive agricultural land released between 2008-2012, 2008-2020 & 2008-2030, including released grassland and fallow land 2012, 2020 & 2030	No yield increase assumed in time. (Uncertainty range about attainable yield levels is already large enough. Adding a yield increase will only increase this uncertainty level and will make the results less transparent)	Maximum volume of land released, so no additional environmental considerations.	Yes, avoidance of competition with food, feed and urbanisation and indirect land use change.	None
Technical (straw & stubbles)	Area in 2012, 2020, 2030 with cereals, rice, sunflower, rape, corn maize	Growth based on regional growing conditions & management. Yield according to regional averages including expected developments in yield towards 2020 and 2030	Maximum volume of straw and stubbles that could be harvested in 2012, 2020 and 2030	None	None
Technical (prunings permanent crops)	Area in 2012, 2020, 2030 with fruit trees, vineyards, olive & citrus	Growth based on regional growing conditions & management. Fruit yield according to regional averages including expected developments in yield towards 2020 and 2030. Input pruning biomass yield averaged by country.	Maximum volume of prunings and cuttings that could be harvested in 2012, 2020 and 2030	None	None
Technical (sugarbeet leaves & tops)	Area in 2012, 2020, 2030 with sugar beet	Growth based on regional growing conditions & management. Yield according to regional averages including expected developments in yield towards 2020 and 2030	Maximum volume of sugar beet leaves and tops that could be harvested in 2012, 2020 and 2030	None	None
Base (dedicated biomass crops)	As in technical potential but excluding land released in HNV	No yield increase assumed in time. (Uncertainty range about attainable	Exclusion of protected areas (NATURA 2000) and HNV farmland and high carbon stock	Yes, avoidance of competition with food, feed and urbanisation and	None

	Area/ Basis	Yield, Growth	Technical & environmental constraints on the biomass retrieval (per area)	Consideration of competing use	Mobilisation
	farmland, NATURA2000, high carbon stock land & permanent grasslands	yield levels is already large enough. Adding a yield increase will only increase this uncertainty level and will make the results less transparent)	lands. No use of land released in permanent grasslands to avoid SOC loss. Adapt crop choice to availability of natural resources such as soil quality and water availability. Irrigation is allowed but only if depletion of fresh water resources is avoided.	indirect land use change.	
Base (straw & stubbles)	As for technical potential	As for technical potential	Only the biomass part can be removed that is not needed to keep the SOC stable. This is assessed according to carbon content that is removed with the residue and the SOC level in the soil that has to be maintained.	None	None
Base (prunings permanent crops)	As for technical potential	As for technical potential		None	None
Base (sugar beet leaves & tops)	As for technical potential	As for technical potential	Removal of leaves and tops from field is only allowed in Nitrate vulnerable zones where nitrogen surplus needs to be declined through removal of nitrogen rich biomass.	None	None
User potential (straw & stubbles)	As for technical potential	As for technical potential	As in base	In cereal straw a subtraction is applied according to demand for straw for animal bedding & feed . For rice straw, corn stover and sunflower and rape stubbles not competing uses are assumed.	None
Base (dedicated biomass crops)	As in base potential except for exclusion of fallow land up to 10% of arable land share. Fallow above the 10% share can be used for dedicated crops	As in Base	As in base, but additional requirements are for maintenance of at least 10% of arable land share in fallow and no use of irrigation allowed in dedicated cropping	As in Base	None
User potential (prunings & cuttings)-	As for technical potential	As for technical potential	All pruned material is available that is currently not used to maintain the SOC and fertility of the soil. So the part that is now removed to the side of the field for energy uses or that is burned with or without energy recovery is seen as potential. This follows the common treatment practices of prunings as assessed in the EuroPruning project.	None	The potential that is not used for SOC and fertility maintenance needs to be mobilised gradually as it requires a change in management; it becomes available from 50% in 2012 to 60% in 2020 and 70% in 2030.

2.1.1 Regional and country level results

Agricultural biomass potentials in EU and neighbouring countries have been assessed building strongly on the CAPRI baseline run 2008-2050, providing intermediate results for 2010, 2020, 2030 and 2050. This baseline run can be seen as the most probable future simulating the European agricultural sector under status-quo policy and including all future changes in policy already foreseen in the current legislation. It also assumes all policy regarding bioenergy targets as agreed until now and further specified in the *Trends to 2050* report (EC, 2013) for as far as affecting agriculture. CAPRI is the only available model which predicts (for 2010, 2020 and 2030) the EU markets and production responses at the regional level for the whole EU-28, western Balkans, Turkey and Norway.

For the assessment of residues (straw, stubbles and pruning residues) the CAPRI land use patterns for 2010 were extrapolated to 2012 using FSS farm structural data and calculating relative crop area (and livestock number) changes between 2010 and 2012 and using these to extrapolate the CAPRI base data 2010 to 2012.

Yields and changes in yield levels per region and country in CAPRI for the conventional crops delivering residues are already included in the baseline scenario of CAPRI.

For the assessment of biomass from dedicated crops the CAPRI input was the base for estimating the land no longer used for agriculture. It was assessed by comparing land in agricultural use in 2008 and in 2012, 2020 and 2030 respectively. The net land difference was then taken as the land basis. Only these unused lands are available for these crops and this is then combined with data generated in this project on biomass crop yield simulations and net present value cost calculations (see D1.6). The combination delivers the final biomass crop mix and potential. So, the land claim for these crops takes account of competing uses from other activities such as for food, feed, and urbanisation.

The potential primary agricultural biomass supply in the 37 countries in 2012 is estimated at 525 million tonnes dry matter (Table 8; Annex 1), according to the Base Potential. The potential is projected to decline to 479 million tonnes dm in 2020 and to 484 million tonnes dm in 2030. This implies a relative decline in agricultural potential between 2012 and 2030 of 8%. This is mainly because of a significant decrease in straw potential (-30%) while the dedicated cropping potential increases as the unused land resource is expected to increase (+60%). The decrease in straw potential cannot be offset completely by the increase in dedicated cropping potential. Prunings also decline by 6% between 2012 and 2030, but their amount is relatively small as compared to straw and dedicated crops.

Figure 1 Relative supply from different primary agricultural biomass sources for all S2biom countries (2012)

Figure 2 Relative supply from different primary agricultural biomass sources for all 2biom countries (2030)

For the agricultural residues it is clear that straw and stubbles are by far more important than the prunings from permanent crops. However, in certain countries like

Spain, Italy, Greece and some western Balkans these types of residues may add more significantly. Furthermore, the straw and stubbles show a decline in availability up to 2030 while the pruning residues remain relatively stable in time.

Figure 3 Relative supply from different dedicated biomass crops all S2biom countries (2012)

Figure 4 Relative supply from different dedicated biomass crops all S2biom countries (2030)

In Figure 3 and Figure 4 the relative crop mix of the dedicated crop potential in 2012 and 2030 is presented. It becomes clear that in the mix the lignocellulosic crops strongly dominate above the woody crop types which is related to suitability and cost levels of the crops in different regions. Lignocellulosic crops provide cheaper biomass in more places in Europe where agricultural lands go out of production than SRC species do. Toward 2030 there is also a relative increase in SRC crops expected which is related to increases in land releases in general and more specifically in regions where the suitability for SRC crops is better than for lignocellulosic crops. This is for example the case for countries like Austria, Germany, UK, France and Hungary.

The national distribution of primary agricultural biomass supply is shown in the Figure 1 and Figure 2. It becomes clear that the largest countries with a large surface area dominate such as France, Ukraine, Turkey, Spain and UK. Italy has a modest biomass supply in 2012 given the size of the country.

In 2012 the largest contribution to the supply is coming from straw and stubbles in most countries except for countries where the unused land resource is already large in 2012 (e.g. Turkey, Ukraine, Romania, Spain, most of western Balkans). Towards 2020 and 2030 the dedicated cropping resource starts to increase in more countries and straw and stubbles generally decline.

The grassland cuttings supply is typical for the UK, Ireland and France. It should be noted, that this resource was only analysed for the EU27, because of lack of data for the rest of the countries. It is based on a nutrient balance and shows the underutilization of grasslands that are (still) part of the farming area. On many (livestock) farms in UK, Ireland, France, Czech Republic, Romania and Poland there seems to be grassland production, which is not fully consumed by the livestock present, making it a biomass resources for non-food uses.

Declines in agricultural biomass supply are most prominent for countries where straw and stubbles are a major part of the potential in 2012 and where there is less unused land resource coming available towards 2020 and 2030 to compensate for the overall decline in residues. This is for example the case in Austria, Belgium, France and Germany.

From Figure 8 it becomes clear that not surprisingly the larger countries have a larger agri-biomass potential. Particularly a country like Ukraine has large potential both for residues and dedicated crops. In countries like France, Poland, Germany we see the same pattern of a serious decline in straw potentials towards 2030 which is largely compensated for by dedicated cropping potential. The UK has a particularly large potential because of the unused grassland cuttings resource. This category is also of great relevance in Ireland and France. It should be remembered however that this potential was only assessed for EU27. So, in the other countries this potential is missing, but it does not mean it is not there.

Figure 5 Total primary agricultural supply (kton dm) by country for the Base Potential in 2012, 2020 and 2030

2.1.2 Spatial distribution of biomass potentials from agriculture

In the following maps the primary agricultural biomass potential is displayed per administrative region (NUTS3 level) and the amount is expressed per unit of land.

The largest potentials of agricultural biomass that also have a high spatial concentration are especially found in regions in northern and central France, central Germany, Northern and middle Ukraine, and southeast England (see maps in Figure 8). There are also regions which in absolute values have large agricultural potentials, but the biomass is more spatially dispersed which is the case in central Turkey, Poland, Czech Republic, Bulgaria, Romania, Spain, southern Sweden and northern England and Scotland and Ireland.

The large amount of agricultural biomass is mostly coming from straw & stubbles from arable crops such as cereals, OSR, sunflower and grain maize as becomes clear from the maps in Figure 9. The largest straw concentration areas are indeed in Northern France, Northern Ukraine, central Germany and East Anglia.

Supply from Agriculture

Supply from Agriculture

Figure 6 Total primary agricultural supply (categories 21, 22, 23; Table 1) at NUTS3 level for the Base potential in 2012 in absolute level (kton dm) (upper map) and in density (ton dm/ha land) (lower map)

Supply from Agriculture

Supply from Agriculture

Figure 7 Total straw and stubble supply (categories 221; Table 1) at NUTS3 level for the Base potential in 2012 in absolute level (kton dm) (upper map) and in density (ton dm/ha land) (lower map)

Supply from Agriculture

Supply from Agriculture

Figure 8 Total pruning supply (categories 222; Table 2) at NUTS3 level for the Base potential in 2012 in absolute level (kton dm) (upper map) and in density (ton dm/ha land) (lower map)

Supply from Agriculture

base_pot

unused_grassland_pot1_yr12

Supply from Agriculture

base_pot

unused_grassland_pot1_yr12

Figure 9 Total grassland cuttings supply (categories 231; Table 2) at NUTS3 level for the Base potential in 2012 in absolute level (kton dm) (upper map) and in density (ton dm/ha land) (lower map)

Supply from Agriculture

Supply from Agriculture

Figure 10 Total dedicated cropping supply (categories 21; Table 2) at NUTS3 level for the Base potential in 2012 in absolute level (Kton dm) (upper map) and in density (ton dm/ha land) (lower map)

The contribution of prunings to the total agricultural potential is very small as compared with straw, but in some southern European countries, particularly Spain this potential can have a meaningful level and spatial concentration (see Figure 10).

Another reason why the pruning potential is considerably smaller than the straw potential is the overall lower sustainable removal rates for prunings as compared to straw. In the base potential the sustainable removal rates require the maintenance of the soil carbon level at a stable state as was assessed through RothC and Miterra-Europe model applications (See S2BIOM Deliverable report D1.6) For straw, this results in a removal rate of around 60% in the Mediterranean countries, while this is only around 33% for prunings. In Atlantic countries the straw removal rates are around 60% while for prunings it is only around 20%.

The results obtained with RothC and Miterra-Europe models (D2Biom Deliverable report D1.7) cause the base potential of agricultural pruning to be about 35% of the technical potential as an average in Europe, some countries like Greece, Portugal or Slovenia show an even lower share. In general Mediterranean countries, where the annual rainfall is much smaller, show lower removal rates. In non-Mediterranean countries the relation between the base and the technical potential is in general much larger, averaging between 60% to 70%. The use of water and the low carbon content are limiting factors under rainfed conditions in Mediterranean countries. However, under irrigated regimes, both issues tend to improve. Therefore, the low base potential should be interpreted as an indicator of potential soil vulnerability for permanent crop plantations. A higher share of the base potential can be achieved, but the use of pruning wood should be accompanied with an examination of the soil conditions, and other agronomic practices leading to the maintenance or increase of the soil organic carbon.

Finally, it should also be realized that the pruning potentials only refer to the biomass that is removed through yearly conventional pruning activities in permanent crops. The biomass that can result from the clearing of a permanent crop plantation at the end of the life-time was not covered in the potential estimates.

An interesting category is also unused grassland cuttings (Figure 11). It should be remembered that this potential was only assessed for EU-27 countries (given data availability). It does not mean this potential is not available in many non-EU countries, but it could simply not be assessed. From the maps in Figure 11 it becomes clear that this potential is very high in Northern England, Scotland and Ireland but also interesting amounts should be available in several regions in France, Romania, Czech Republic and Austria.

Dedicated cropping potentials are largest in several regions in central Spain, Turkey, Bosnia, Bulgaria and Romania (see Figure 12). In these regions there is a large unused land resource already in 2012. The dedicated cropping potential is the most uncertain potential in the agricultural biomass group as it first requires setting up dedicated cropping plantations. The potentials shown for 2012 are basically only

pinpointing to the regions with a large unused land resource as assessed in this study based on the CAPRI land use requirements. It is more interesting to look at potentials for dedicated cropping in the intermediate future 2020 and 2030 (see Figure 13) as the trend is towards a large increase in unused lands towards 2020 and a slight decline again towards 2030. The largest dedicated cropping potentials are mostly found in Spain, most CEEC countries, western Balkans, Turkey and Ukraine. These potential remain however most uncertain as they require serious collaboration and investments to bring abandoned agricultural lands in production again.

Supply from Agriculture

Supply from Agriculture

Figure 11 Total dedicated cropping supply (categories 21; Table 2) at NUTS3 level for the Base potential in 2020 (upper map) and 2030 (lower map) in absolute level (kton dm)

2.1.3 Cost levels & potentials

The supply costs were estimated only for the **road side cost**, so any cost made for transport and pre-treatment between the road side and the conversion plant gate.

All cost presented in the next maps for agricultural biomass types was calculated with the *Activity Based Costing* (ABC) model. The general purpose of this model is to provide minimum cost prices for the primary production of biomass feedstock at the road side. ABC generates the costs of different components based on specific input and output associated with the choice of the means of production, varying with the local conditions and cost of inputs (e.g. labour, energy, fertilisers, lubricants etc.). Since the production of most biomass is spread over several years, often long term cycles in which cost are incurred continuously while harvest only takes place once in so many years, the Net Present Values (NPV) of the future costs are calculated. Road side cost are presented as NPV per annum and expressed in € per ton dm.

The cost also allow for national differentiation of cost according to main inputs having national specific prices levels. National level price data (ex. VAT) included cover cost/prices for labour (skilled, unskilled and average), fuel, electricity, fertilizers (N, P2O5, K2), machinery, water, crop protection and land. Most of these data were gathered from statistical sources such as FADN (Farm Accountancy Data Network), Eurostat and OECD. Most cost levels were gathered for the year 2012.

In S2Biom only the costs specifically made to produce the biomass for the non-feed or -food markets are considered. This means that in cases where there is a crop production for human consumption or for feed involved, such as wheat, this production will be considered the main product and the biomass for non-feed or food (e.g. straw in case of wheat) the by-product. All costs of growing the crop are attributed to the main product and consequently these become sunken costs for the by-product and thus excluded. Only activities specifically dedicated to the by-product (e.g. harvesting the straw) add to the (minimum) cost level of the biomass feedstock.

In the case of straw these cost include harvesting, fertilization, because of nutrient removal with the straw, and baling and forwarding to the road side/farm gate. In the case of prunings this involves the cost for treatment and collection of the branches left on the soil, as shredded material to road side. It involves collection, shredding and forwarding to road side. In the case of dedicated biomass crops the cost structure is clear and all cost can be allocated to the final product which is the biomass. All cost should include the fixed and variable cost of producing the biomass including land, machinery, seeds, input costs and on field harvesting costs. In the case of unused grassland cuttings the cost consist of mowing, racking which is needed to dry the cuttings before baling, baling and collection and loading at the road side.

Figure 12 Cost and supply levels- for straw & stubbles

In Figure 12 the cost supply combination is given of all primary agricultural biomass. It shows that the lowest weighted average road-side cost (<25€/ton dm) for agricultural biomass are found in Ukraine and most western Balkan countries. Intermediate cost levels (25-50 €/ton dm) are particularly found in Hungary, Bulgaria, Romania, Croatia, Czech Republic, Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania, Slovakia and Turkey. The remaining countries have higher cost levels where the highest cost levels (>100 €/ton dm) are found in Austria, Finland, Germany, Sweden and Denmark.

The higher cost levels are especially related with high overall national price levels for inputs like labour and machinery. The mix of biomass types that builds up the weighted average cost levels is also very important. Overall lowest cost levels are for straw, followed by unused grassland cuttings. Biomass from dedicated crops is generally in the middle range, although differences in national cost levels are very large. The most expensive cost levels are for prunings. Small fields and small row distances between the crops can make the collection of this type of biomass very cost intensive as mechanisation of it is a challenge in small scale fields (see Figure 13).

Figure 13 Cost and supply levels- for prunings

The only countries where cost for prunings are still within a reasonable range is Ukraine (around 40 €/ton dm) and in most Western Balkan countries (around 60 €/ton dm). On the other hand these pruning cost may be an over estimation in case farmers prefer to remove prunings from the field any way. A reason is that removal of pruning material should be seen as normal practice as it helps to decline the risk for pest. The organisation of the value chain may require that farmers internalise part of the costs for collection, shredding and forwarding of the pruning material: in other words, to understand that the use of pruning for energy is an alternative of the pruning management leading to potential savings in the overall exploitation costs of the plantation. Under this view farmers may accept to get less return for the pruning part collected for energy (see Figure 14).

Supply from Agriculture

final_feedstocks_costs

dedicated

base_pot

dedicated_pot1_yr20

Figure 14 Cost and supply levels- for dedicated crops

Unused grassland cuttings are a not too expensive biomass resource as compared to other primary agricultural sources (see Figure 15). This resource may also be in relevance in the other non-EU countries where it could not be investigated because of data limitations. It is however a resource that needs further attention in new research. Countries that have a large resource such as UK, Ireland, but also some regions in France should investigate whether this resource can indeed be mobilised and what the environmental gains and risks are of exploiting it.

Supply from Agriculture

final_feedstocks_costs

unused_grassland

- <25
- 25-50
- 50-75
- 75-100
- 100-150
- >150 euro per ton

base_pot

unused_grassland_pot1_yr12

- 0
- >0 - 0.1
- 0.1 - 0.25
- 0.25 - 0.5
- 0.5 - 0.75
- 0.75 - 1
- 1 - 1.5
- 1.5 - 3
- > 3 ton dm/ha

Figure 15 Cost and supply levels- for unused grassland cuttings

2.2 Wood production and primary residues from forests map

2.2.1 Introduction

Wood production and primary residues from forests comprises the categories presented in Table 3.

Table 3 Subcategories of first level category 1 “Forestry”

Second level subcategories		Third level subcategories		Final level subcategories	
ID	Name	ID	Name	ID	Name
11	Primary production from forests	111	Stemwood from final fellings & thinnings	1111	Stemwood from final fellings originating from non-conifer tree species
				1112	Stemwood from final fellings originating from conifer tree species
				1113	Stemwood from thinnings originating from non-conifer tree species
				1114	Stemwood from thinnings originating from conifer tree species
12	Primary residues from forests	121	Logging residues from final fellings & thinnings	1211	Logging residues from final fellings from non-conifer tree species
				1212	Logging residues from final fellings from conifer tree species
				1213	Logging residues from thinnings from non-conifer tree species
				1214	Logging residues from thinnings from conifer tree species
		122	Stumps from final fellings	1221	Stumps from final fellings originating from non-conifer tree species
				1222	Stumps from final fellings originating from conifer tree species

The results presented here highlight the categories “Forestry” “Production from forests” and “Primary residues from forests”. The third and final level sub-categories are presented in the online tool only.

The estimated potential supply and its cost are presented here in form of graphs, maps and tables (Annex) in accordance with the definitions of the potential levels as specified in the methods report D1.6 comprising technical, base and user defined potentials. These potentials types are defined as shown in Table 4.

Table 4 Overview of the major woody biomass potential types used in S2BIOM

Name	Area/ Basis	Yield, Growth	Technical & environmental constraints on the biomass retrieval (per area)	Consideration of competing use	Mobilisation
TP - Technical	Default: Forest area available for wood supply. This excludes protected and protective areas, where harvesting is not allowed according to protection purpose.	Default: Growth based on regional to national growing conditions, including changes in biomass increment due to climate change. Yield according to regional management guidelines for age limits for thinnings and final fellings.	Maximum volume of stemwood that could be harvested annually during 50-year periods. Technical constraints on residue and stump extraction (recovery rate)	Default: None	Default: None
HP - High			As for technical potential, but considering additional constraints (but less stringent as compared to base potential) for residue and stump extraction: Site productivity -Soil and water protection: ruggedness, soil depth, soil surface texture, soil compaction risk -Biodiversity (protected forest areas) -Soil bearing capacity.		
BP - Base			Default: As for technical potential, but considering additional constraints (based on current biomass harvesting guidelines) for residue and stump extraction: -Site productivity -Soil and water protection: ruggedness, soil depth, soil surface texture, soil compaction risk -Biodiversity (protected forest areas) -Soil bearing capacity.		
UP1 - User potential - option 1	Reduction of FAWS by 5% (due to increased forest protection)	Default	Default	Default	Default
UP2 - User potential - option 2	Reduction of FAWS by 5% (due to increased forest protection)	Default	Increase in retained trees by 5%.	Default	Default
UP3 - User potential - option 3	Default	Default	No stump extraction.	Default	Default
UP4 - User potential - option 4	Reduction of FAWS by 5% (due to increased forest protection)	Default	Increase in retained trees by 5% plus no stump extraction	Default	Default
UP5 - User potential - option 5	Default	Default	Default	Total roundwood production for material use subtracted.	Default
UP6 - User potential - option 6	Default	Default	Default	Roundwood production for material use (excluding production of pulp and paper and board industry) subtracted.	Default
UP7 - User potential - option 7	Reduction of FAWS by 5% (due to increased forest protection)	Default	Increase in retained trees by 5% plus no stump extraction	Total roundwood production for material use subtracted.	Default
UP8 - User potential - option 8	Reduction of FAWS by 5% (due to increased forest protection)	Default	Increase in retained trees by 5% plus no stump extraction	Roundwood production for material use (excluding production of pulp and paper and board industry) subtracted.	Default

Note: the Base Potential contains all default assumptions, for which variations are assumed in the User Potentials. Default assumptions apply to all potential types, unless stated otherwise.

All potentials are defined in detail in S2BIOM deliverable 1.6. In the section below we mainly focus on the Base Potential (BP).

2.2.2 Regional and country level results

Woody biomass potentials from forests in the EU and neighbouring countries have been estimated using the EFISCEN forest resource model, as well as international forestry statistics. The potential supply of woody biomass in these 37 countries in 2012 is estimated at 379 million tonnes dry matter yr⁻¹ overbark (or 817 million m³ yr⁻¹ overbark; Table 15 and Table 16.

in Annex 1), according to the Base Potential. The potential was projected to decrease by 2.1% to 370 million tonnes dry matter yr⁻¹ overbark by 2030, but in general the potential was rather stable over time. This is mainly because the potential for each year is based on the average maximum harvest level that can be maintained throughout the next 50-year period. About 88% of the total potential is in stems, while logging residues and stumps represent 12% (Figure 16 and Figure 17). The majority of this potential is located within the 28 EU member states; the potential supply of woody biomass for the Base Potential from EU forests is estimated at 337 million tonnes dry matter yr⁻¹ overbark (or 728 million m³ yr⁻¹ overbark).

Figure 16 Proportions of supply from forestry- Base Potentials for all S2biom countries (2012)

Figure 17 Proportions of supply from forestry - Base Potentials for EU28 (2012)

Figure 18 Total forestry potentials (categories 11 and 12; Table 3) by country for the Base Potential in 2012, 2020 and 2030

The woody biomass potentials are not equally distributed between the 37 countries (Figure 18). The four countries that have the largest forest biomass potentials (Sweden, Germany, France and Finland) represent about 45% of the total potential supply of the study area. The large potentials for these countries are related to the extent of their forest areas.

The potential supply of woody biomass according to other forestry potential types (i.e. when assuming other constraints that reduce the potential supply) are shown in Figure 19, Figure 20 and Figure 21. The Technical Potential, High Potential and Base Potential vary only in terms of potential availability of primary residues (i.e. logging residues and stumps) from forests. Only for the User Potentials there are differences in the amount of stemwood as compared to the Base Potential, due to assumptions on increases of the protected forest area and retention trees and on the uses of wood.

Figure 19 Total forestry potentials (categories 11 and 12; Table 3) by country for the Base Potential (BP), High Potential (HP), Technical Potential (TP) and User Potential 4 (UP4) in 2012

Figure 20 Total forestry potentials (categories 11 and 12; Table 3) by country for the Base Potential (BP) and User Potentials 5 and 7 (UP5, UP7) in 2012²

² The view occurring negative values (see Annex A4) are set to zero in this figure.)

Figure 21 Total forestry potentials [primary forestry production plus primary residues from forests] (categories 11 and 12; Table 3) by country User Potentials 4, 6 and 8 (UP4, UP6 and UP8) in 2012

2.2.3 Spatial distribution of biomass potentials from forests

To gain insight into the spatial distribution of these potentials, the maps in Figure 22 to Figure 26 show biomass potentials for administrative regions (NUTS-3 level). To be able to compare potentials between regions and with potentials from other sources (e.g. agriculture, other land uses) potentials are displayed per unit of land.

The largest potential supply of woody biomass per unit of land can be found in Northern Europe (southern Finland and Sweden, Estonia and Latvia), Central Europe (Austria, Czech Republic, and Southern Germany), southwest France and Portugal. The forest biomass potentials per unit of land (Figure 17) are generally highest in Central and Northern Europe, due to higher forest productivity (mainly Central Europe, southwest France and Portugal) and a higher forest cover ratio (mainly Northern Europe). Conversely, the biomass potentials per unit of land are generally low in Southern European countries due to lower productivity of the forest resources, as well as in countries that have only a low share of forest cover (Denmark, Ireland, the Netherlands, and United Kingdom).

Supply from Forests [2012]

Base Potential

tonnes/ha

S2Biom

Figure 22 Total forestry supply potential (categories 11 and 12; Table 3) per ha of land at NUTS-3 level for the Base potential in 2012

Supply from Forests [2020]

Base Potential

tonnes/ha

S2Biom

Figure 23 Total forestry potential (categories 11 and 12; Table 3) per ha of land at NUTS-3 level for the Base potential in 2020

Supply from Forests [2030]

Base Potential

tonnes/ha

Figure 24 Total forestry potential (categories 11 and 12; Table 3) per ha of land at NUTS-3 level for the Base potential in 2030

Primary Forestry Production [2012]

Base Potential

tonnes/ha

Figure 25 Potential from primary forestry production potential (i.e. stemwood; category 11; Table 3) per ha of land at NUTS-3 level for the Base potential in 2012

Primary Residues from Forests [2012]

Base Potential

tonnes/ha

Figure 26 Potential from primary residues (i.e. logging residues and stumps, category 12; Table 3) per ha of land at NUTS-3 level for the Base potential in 2012[^]

2.2.4 Cost levels & potentials

The supply costs were estimated up to the roadside including chipping or crushing, but excluding road transport and production costs. The methodology of cost estimation consists of two main components: 1) the estimation of hourly machine costs, and 2) the estimation of work productivity. In order to enable better comparison of costs between regions, supply chains were standardised. The dominant supply chain for stemwood in Europe is the chain based on roadside chipping. In the chain felling and bunching are carried out by a harvester, off-road transport by a forwarder and chipping by a mobile chipper. For logging residues the chain is otherwise similar except for the missing felling phase. Instead, piling of logging residues by the harvester is considered to belong to logging residue supply chain. Stumps are extracted by an excavator, forwarded to roadside and crushed by a mobile grinder.

In the estimation of machine costs both machine-level and country-level input data were used as explanatory variables in the costing model applied in the study. The machine-level data included, e.g., fuel consumption and the country-level data variables like purchase price, fuel cost and labour cost.

In the estimation of productivity a set of productivity models were selected for the following work phases: mechanized felling and bunching, integrated bunching while felling with a harvester, forwarding, chipping, stump lifting, and crushing. Subsequently, data describing the operating environment were collected and used as explanatory variables for the productivity models. Examples of such data included the intensity of harvesting on a felling area, average size of the removed trees and slope.

All the cost estimations pertain to the cost level of 2012. For a complete description of the methodology see Dees et al. (2017).

As Figure 27 to Figure 34 show, generally, the supply costs in Eastern Europe tend to be lower than elsewhere in the study area. Further work would be needed to thoroughly analyse which of the explanatory variables are the most influential to the costs. However, the lower costs in Eastern Europe can – at least to a certain extent – be explained by lower investment, fuel and especially labour costs.

In Western Europe Denmark, Italy and Ireland stand out from the neighbouring countries with respect to the supply cost of stemwood from final fellings (Figure 27). This might be due to the small tree size, relatively long forwarding distances and – in Italy – steep terrain. The supply costs of logging residues from final fellings seem to be especially high in Romania, Greece and Italy, possibly owing to the long forwarding distances. Furthermore, small tree size explains the exceptionally high supply cost of non-conifer stemwood from thinnings in Ukraine and in Latvia.

Cost Supply: Stemwood from Final Fellings (Conifers)

2012 Base Potential

Cost Levels [EUR/m³]

- No Data
- 7 - 10
- 10 - 12
- 12 - 14
- 14 - 16
- 16 - 18
- > 18

Supply Levels [m³/ha]

- 0
- > 0 - 0.05
- 0.05 - 0.2
- 0.2 - 0.4
- 0.4 - 0.7
- 0.7 - 1.0
- 1.0 - 1.5
- > 1.5

S2Biom

Figure 27 Cost and supply levels- Stemwood from final fellings (conifer)

Cost Supply: Stemwood from Thinnings (Conifers)

2012 Base Potential

Cost Levels [EUR/m³]

- No Data
- 10 - 12
- 12 - 14
- 14 - 16
- 16 - 18
- 18 - 20
- > 20

Supply Levels [m³/ha]

- 0
- > 0 - 0.05
- 0.05 - 0.1
- 0.1 - 0.2
- 0.2 - 0.4
- 0.4 - 0.6
- 0.6 - 0.8
- > 0.8

S2Biom

Figure 28 Cost and supply levels- Stemwood from thinnings (conifer)

Cost Supply: Logging Residues from Final Fellings (Conifers)

2012 Base Potential

Cost Levels [EUR/m³]

- No Data
- 7 - 10
- 10 - 12
- 12 - 14
- 14 - 16
- 16 - 18
- > 18

Supply Levels [m³/ha]

- 0
- > 0 - 0.01
- 0.01 - 0.02
- 0.02 - 0.03
- 0.03 - 0.05
- 0.05 - 0.1
- 0.1 - 0.2
- 0.2 - 0.5
- > 0.5

Figure 29 Cost and supply levels- Residues from final fellings (conifer)

Cost Supply: Stumps from Final Fellings (Conifers)

2012 Base Potential

Cost Levels [EUR/m³]

- No Data
- 22 - 24
- 24 - 26

Supply Levels [m³/ha]

- 0
- > 0 - 0.01
- 0.01 - 0.02
- 0.02 - 0.03
- 0.03 - 0.05
- 0.05 - 0.1
- 0.1 - 0.2
- > 0.2

Figure 30 Cost and supply levels- Stumps from final fellings (conifer)

Cost Supply: Stemwood from Final Fellings (Non-Conifers)

2012 Base Potential

Cost Levels [EUR/m³]

- No Data
- 7 - 10
- 10 - 12
- 12 - 14
- 14 - 16
- 16 - 18
- > 18

Supply Levels [m³/ha]

- 0
- > 0 - 0.05
- 0.05 - 0.2
- 0.2 - 0.4
- 0.4 - 0.7
- 0.7 - 1.0
- 1.0 - 1.5
- > 1.5

Figure 31 Cost and supply levels- Stemwood from final fellings (non-conifer)

Cost Supply: Stemwood from Thinnings (Non-Conifers)

2012 Base Potential

Cost Levels [EUR/m³]

- No Data
- 10 - 12
- 12 - 14
- 14 - 16
- 16 - 18
- 18 - 20
- > 20

Supply Levels [m³/ha]

- 0
- > 0 - 0.05
- 0.05 - 0.1
- 0.1 - 0.2
- 0.2 - 0.4
- 0.4 - 0.6
- 0.6 - 0.8
- > 0.8

Figure 32 Cost and supply levels- Stemwood from thinnings (non-conifer)

Cost Supply: Logging Residues from Final Fellings (Non-Conifers)

2012 Base Potential

Cost Levels [EUR/m³]

- No Data
- 9 - 10
- 10 - 12
- 12 - 14
- 14 - 16
- 16 - 18
- > 18

Supply Levels [m³/ha]

- 0
- > 0 - 0.01
- 0.01 - 0.02
- 0.02 - 0.03
- 0.03 - 0.05
- 0.05 - 0.1
- 0.1 - 0.2
- 0.2 - 0.5
- > 0.5

Figure 33 Cost and supply levels- Residues from final fellings (non-conifer)

Cost Supply: Stumps from Final Fellings (Non-Conifers)

2012 Base Potential

Cost Levels [EUR/m³]

- No Data
- 24 - 26
- 26 - 28
- 28 - 30

Supply Levels [m³/ha]

- 0
- > 0 - 0.01
- 0.01 - 0.02
- 0.02 - 0.03
- 0.03 - 0.05
- 0.05 - 0.1
- 0.1 - 0.2
- > 0.2

Figure 34 Cost and supply levels- Stumps from final fellings (non-conifer)

2.3 Other land use

The biomass category covered for 'other land use' is the road side verge grass.

Table 5 Subcategories of biomass from other land use

Second level subcategories		Third level subcategories		Final level subcategories	
ID	Name	ID	Name	ID	Name
		312	Biomass from road side verges	3121	Grassy biomass from road side verges

It's distribution over Europe is quite even, but the spatial concentration is rather low as compared to other biomass types like straw or primary forest residues.

Supply from Agriculture

base_pot

roadside_verge_grass_pot1_yr12

Supply from Agriculture

base_pot

roadside_verge_grass_pot1_yr12

Figure 35 Potential from road side verge grass (category 312; Table 5) at NUTS-3 level for the Base potential in 2012 in absolute level (Kton dm) (upper map) and in density (ton dm/ha land) (lower map)

2.3.1 Cost levels other land uses

The cost level of road side verge grass have also been assessed with the ABC model and the cost allocated consist of mowing, racking, baling and collection and loading. Although the cost for mowing is part of normal road side management we still allocate these cost to the cuttings because we expect higher mowing frequency if cuttings have a use. Collection and loading at the road side can be a time consuming activity because it needs to be done along a road, where traffic can be busy and space to work limited. The cost levels are in the range of 25 to 100 €/ton dm over Europe (See Figure 36).

Figure 36 Cost and supply levels- from road side verge grass

2.4 Secondary residues from wood industry

2.4.1 Introduction

Secondary forest residues (SFR) comprise residues from saw mills, from pulp and paper industry and from other wood processing sectors. The full list of subcategories considered is presented in Table 6.

Table 6 Subcategories of Secondary residues from wood industries

SFR subcategories	SFR final level subcategories
Saw mill residues	Sawdust from sawmills from conifers
	Sawdust from sawmills from nonconifers
	Sawmill residues: excluding sawdust, conifers
	Sawmill residues: excluding sawdust, nonconifers
Other wood processing industry residues	Residues from industries producing semi -finished wood based panels
	Residues from further wood processing
Secondary residues from pulp and paper industry	Bark residues from pulp and paper industry
	Black liquor

The potentials have been derived mainly from production data, factors on round wood input and share of residues. The technical and the base potential are identical since no further than technical constraints have been considered in the base potential definition.

In addition two user defined potential levels have been determined. For the user defined potential option 1 “UP1” residues from saw mill industry that are utilised by other wood industry sectors, board and pulp and paper namely, are not considered since they are used there for product generation for material use. This potential thus allows the determination of the potential of SFR for the utilisation for energy and new biobased materials production. The user defined potential option 2 “UP2” differs in the scope of industrial sectors that can share this potential in completion. It is defined for the determination of the potential from forestry *plus* SFR for the sectors energy, new biobased materials production, pulp and paper, and board production, when user defined potentials from forestry, that are accordingly defined are utilised. It excludes residues from the pulp paper and the board industry. The residues from further wood processing are not considered either, since they partly originate from the board industry.

More on the methods applied to determine SFR are provided in the S2BIOM Deliverable 1.6 (Dees et al. 2017).

The general shares of the main residue streams within SFR are shown on the example of the base potential in 2012 for all S2BIOM countries in Figure 37 and for EU28 in Figure 38. Residues from sawmill industry are dominating with over 40%, followed by pulp and paper residues with over 30% whereas other wood processing residues built the smallest but still considerable fraction with over 20%.

Figure 37 Proportions of supply from secondary forestry residues- base potentials for all S2BIOM countries (2012)

Figure 38 Proportions of supply from secondary forestry residues- base potentials for EU28 (2012)

Detailed results per major category per country and time scale are provided in the tables in the Annex of this report and are as well available via the online tool.

2.4.2 Regional and country level results

The availability of SFR is depending on the production of the wood industry per country. This gets visible in Figure 39 that shows the SFR potentials from saw mill residues, other wood processing industries and from pulp and paper industry for 2012 to 2030.

The highest amounts are available in Sweden, Finland and Germany (together these countries provide nearly 50% of the potential of EU28) followed by Poland, France and Austria (together these six countries provide about 2/3 of the potential of EU28), this in accordance with their well established wood industry sectors. Figure 39 further clearly shows the high impact of the existence and strength of the pulp and paper industry on the availability of SFR per country.

The expected development per sector is based on the base scenario predictions in the study EFSOS II, except for the pulp and paper sector that is assumed to remain stable. The growth differs per country in accordance with the EFOSOS II projections (Figure 39) and is in single countries negative. Still, in total there is in EU28 for 2020 an increase by 3.6% vs. 2012 and for 2030 by 6.3 % vs. 2012. In the non EU-countries there is a stronger increase towards 2020 by 10.6% and towards 2030 by 20.0%. Figure 40 illustrates the difference between the potential levels that show the highest differences in countries with a high pulp and paper industry.

Figure 39 Wood industry base potentials by country for 2012, 2020 and 2030

Figure 40 Wood industry potentials by country for 2012, all potential levels in comparison

2.4.3 NUTS3-Maps

As already mentioned for the country totals there is only a slight increase from 2012 towards 2030 and that gets visible in the maps on the SFR total potential in Figure 41, Figure 42 and Figure 43. The spatial distribution in these figures shows that the dominating countries and regions are in the Nordic Countries and Central Europe.

The figures by major origin of SFR show that for sawmill industries the highest density of SFR are available in the Nordic countries, Germany, Poland and Austria (Figure 44). A relative similar spatial distribution can be observed for pulp and paper industry residues with a clear concentration at administrative units, where pulp and paper mills are located (Figure 45). Figure 46 shows a high impact of the population density since further wood processing industries are by the methodology assumed to be related to the population density and these *further* wood processing residues within *other* wood processing industries contribute to the total on average a share larger than 80%.

Secondary Residues from Wood Industries [2012]

Base Potential

tonnes/ha

Figure 41 Secondary residues from wood industries per ha of land at NUTS-3 level for the Base potential in 2012

Secondary Residues from Wood Industries [2020]

Base Potential

tonnes/ha

Figure 42 Secondary residues from wood industries per ha of land at NUTS-3 level for the Base potential in 2020

Secondary Residues from Wood Industries [2030]

Base Potential

tonnes/ha

Figure 43 Secondary residues from wood industries per ha of land at NUTS-3 level for the Base potential in 2030

Secondary Residues from Sawmill Industry [2012]

Base Potential

tonnes/ha

Figure 44 Secondary residues from saw mill industry per ha of land at NUTS-3 level for the Base potential in 2012

Secondary Residues from Pulp and Paper Industry [2012]

Base Potential

tonnes/ha

Figure 45 Secondary residues from pulp and paper industry per ha of land at NUTS-3 level for the Base potential in 2012

Secondary Residues from Other Wood Processing Industry [2012]

Base Potential

tonnes/ha

Figure 46 Secondary residues from other wood processing industries per ha of land at NUTS-3 level for the Base potential in 2012

2.5 Secondary residues of industry utilising agricultural products

For secondary agro-industrial residues four types of biomass have been covered as presented in Table 7. Only one type of potential was assessed for these residues which can both be seen as the technical and the base potential.

Their total in Europe amounts to almost 35,000 Kton dm. The lion share comes from cereal bran, which is not surprising given that the bran comes from both domestically grown and imported cereals processed in Europe.

Table 7 Subcategories of secondary agricultural residues

Second level subcategories		Third level subcategories		Final level subcategories	
ID	Name	ID	Name	ID	Name
42	<i>Secondary residues of industry utilising agricultural products</i>	421	By-products and residues from food and fruit processing industry	4211	Olive-stones
				4213	Rice husk
				4214	Pressed grapes residues
				4215	Cereal bran

Since more than 90% of the agri-industrial residues are made up of cereal bran the mapped potentials are only presented for this biomass types in Figure 47. As becomes clear, the overall agro-industrial residues spatial concentration is limited, but there are regions, particularly large port regions where large domestic and imported cereal grains are processed. Rice husk concentrations are found in northwest Italy and southern Spain, the main rice producing areas in Europe. Pressed grape dregs are where there is wine production, but overall amounts are small. The same applies to olive pits of course found where olives are produced. The processing of olive usually takes place in the region where the olives are produced, so it implies a rather large spatial dispersion of its residues.

Supply from Agriculture

Supply from Agriculture

Figure 47 Cereal bran potential in absolute value (Kton dm) (upper map) and in density (Kton/ha of land) (lower map) at NUTS-3 level for the Base potential in 2012

2.6 Waste collection/ tertiary residues

2.6.1 Introduction

Biowaste and post-consumer wood are the most relevant lignocellulosic tertiary waste streams. Figure 48 and Figure 49 show that mass distribution between biowaste and post-consumer wood and their fractions in all the S2BIOM countries and the EU28, respectively. In this section both potentials are shortly introduced, presented and discussed.

Figure 48 Pie Chart showing the total waste (biowaste and post consumer wood) supply distribution from base potentials (2012) for all S2biom countries (mass based)

Figure 49 Pie Chart showing the total waste (biowaste and post consumer wood) supply distribution from base potentials (2012) for EU28 (mass based)

2.6.2 Regional and country level results

Biowaste

Biowaste is defined as “biodegradable garden and park waste, food and kitchen waste from households, restaurants, catering and retail premises and comparable waste from food processing plants” (Waste Framework Directive (2008/98/EC)). Biowaste is part of biodegradable municipal waste, but it excludes textile and separately collected paper and paperboard. Biowaste can be separately collected or be part of integrally collected municipal waste. Separately collected biowaste can generate energy by anaerobic digestion followed by composting. Integrally collected biowaste can be incinerated with energy generation, or part of the biowaste can be separated as part of “refuse derived fuel” and subsequently combusted in a bioenergy plant. The choice for separate or integral collection of biowaste strongly depends on the waste policy of the EU country, which can be either more directed to separate collection and composting (plus option for digestion) or to integral collection and processing (including combustion). Both are accepted options as long as the material is not incinerated without energy generation or being landfilled.

Because of this strong link between waste collection system and energy potential (separate collection & anaerobic digestion versus integral collection & combustion/incineration) only one energy potential is provided linked to the current and expected future waste management practises of the countries as analysed in Arcadis and Eunomia (2009) and population growth. Figure 50 shows the production of biowaste per year in the different European countries. The expected growth or decline in biowaste production is linked with the population growth in these countries, and is rather stable.

No difference has been made between the technical potential and base potential as all collected waste is in principle available for energy generation. No user-defined potential has been defined as options to optimise for energy generation are limited. For instance, it does not make sense to assume a potential level in which all countries change from a separate collection to an integral collection scheme, just for the sake of energy generation and abolishing composting.

Figure 50 Biowaste production in 2012, 2020 and 2030

Post-consumer wood

Post-consumer wood (PCW) includes all kinds of wooden material that is available at the end of its use as a wooden product (“post-consumer” or “post-use” wood). Post-consumer recovered wood mainly comprises packaging materials (e.g. pallets), demolition wood, timber from building sites, and fractions of used wood from residential (municipal waste), industrial and commercial activities. Post-consumer wood is a tertiary raw material, which should be collected, sorted and re-utilised or recycled and finally used for energy production.

Figure 51 shows that the (base) potential of post-consumer wood rises in most countries between 2012 and 2030. The growth rates are based on projections made in the EU wood project (EU27)³ and EFSOS II (other European countries)⁴.

³ Mantau U et.al.; EUwood, Real potential for changes in growth and use of EU forests, Methodology report June 2010

⁴ UNECE (United Nations Economic Commission for Europe), FAO (Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations) 2011: The European Forest Sector Outlook Study II; Geneva

Figure 51 The development of the supply of post-consumer wood in 2012, 2020 and 2030 (base potential)

The technical, base and user-defined potentials of post-consumer wood of 2020 and 2030 are presented in Figure 52 and Figure 53, respectively.

The *technical potential* assumes that all collectable post-consumer wood can be collected used for energy generation. About 5% of available post-consumer wood cannot be recovered for technical reasons.

The *base potential* shows the potential for energy generation, taking into account the current use of post-consumer wood for material applications, currently mainly particleboard production. Obviously, the base potential is in most cases much lower than the technical potential, as the latter does not take into account current material use of post-consumer wood.

The *user-defined potential* shows how much wood would remain available for energy if increased cascading use in 2020 and 2030 is respected. The Circular Economy Package proposes a target of 75% of material recycling of packaging wood in 2030, this will be a challenge but the quality of packaging waste (mainly clean sawn wood) is suitable for recycling. The other waste wood fractions are more difficult to recycle; there are not too many options to recycle used panels (particle board, MDF, OSB, plywood). Recycling rates of other wood (besides packaging) are not expected to exceed 50%. This results in an overall material application of non hazardous post-

consumer wood of 49.2%⁵ in 2020 and 61.5%⁶ in 2030. Moreover, all hazardous waste wood is assumed to be available for energy generation. The difference between the user-defined scenario of increased cascading use of wood and the base scenario base potential depends on the historical shares of energy, material and disposal of post-consumer wood on country level:

- In Denmark, Germany and Sweden the used defined potential is lower than the base potential because these countries have currently a high energy utilisation of post-consumer wood, which would be reduced in the user-defined scenario with increased material application of wood in 2020 and 2030.
- In countries like Czech Republic, Estonia, Greece, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Portugal, Romania and Slovenia currently much wood is still disposed, which is in case of the user-defined scenario will be partly allocated to material application in 2020 and 2030. This results in a lower user-defined potential compared to the base scenario, in which all currently disposed wood is allocated to energy use.
- In case of a tradition of high material utilisation and a low disposal rate, the difference between base potential and user-defined potential is zero. In this case the base potential (that takes into account current material application) meets already the assumptions on increased material consumption of the user-defined potential. This is the case in countries like Austria, France and Italy.

⁵ Assuming 60% material application of used packaging wood and 40% of the other wood in 2020.

⁶ Assuming 75% material application of used packaging wood and 50% of the other wood in 2030.

Figure 52 Technical, base and user-defined potential of post-consumer wood in 2020

Figure 53 Technical, base and user-defined potential of post-consumer wood in 2030

Figure 54 shows the development of the user-defined potential in time, showing that despite the increased material consumption assumed in this scenario, in most countries the energy potential increases compared to the baseline scenario in 2012⁷, due the growth of post-consumer wood production as forecasted in EFSOS II and EUwood. Main exceptions are the countries with both a high energy utilisation and high recovery rate of post-consumer wood such as Germany and Sweden. However, in general this scenario shows that despite increased cascading use (UD1 scenario), biomass availability for energy will grow in most countries in 2020 and 2030 compared to 2012. Moreover, this scenario does not take into account that after its lifetime in the material sector post-consumer wood comes back to the energy sector for energy generation. Therefore, after some decades the availability of post-consumer wood for energy would increase even more.

Figure 54 User-defined potential in 2012, 2020 and 2030

⁷ Note that the User Defined potential is defined only for 2020 and 2030; this means that UP1 2012 equals the base scenario BP 2012.

2.6.1 NUTS3-Maps

The data on biowaste and post-consumer wood has been collected on country level. The disaggregation of the results at NUTS3 (municipal) level has been performed based on the population of these regions, as population is the best indicator for waste generation. However, within the limits of this study it was not possible to distinguish between rural and urban areas or between regions with more or less construction with wood within countries. Therefore, the NUTS3 maps give just an indication of the biowaste and post-consumer wood available within the regions. The biomass densities in the maps show a strong correlation with the population density in the different areas of Europe (Figure 55 to Figure 59).

Figure 55 Waste (Biowaste and Post Consumer Wood), Base potential 2012

Supply from Biowaste and Post Consumer Wood [2020]

Base Potential

tonnes/ha

Figure 56 Waste (Biowaste and Post Consumer Wood), Base potential 2020

Supply from Biowaste and Post Consumer Wood [2030]

Base Potential

tonnes/ha

Figure 57 Waste (Biowaste and Post Consumer Wood), Base potential 2030

Supply from Biowaste [2012]

Base Potential

tonnes/ha

Figure 58 Biowaste, Base potential 2012

Supply from Post Consumer Wood [2012]

Base Potential

tonnes/ha

Figure 59 Post Consumer Wood, Base potential 2012

2.7 Import of biomass resources

2.7.1 Introduction

For import of biomass resources, the import potential is here presented in the form of cost supply curves. One set of cost supply curves define how much biomass can be imported to Europe from the rest of the world for bioenergy purposes (mainly heat and electricity), and one curve define the potential import of biofuels. Though the two cost supply curves differ in terms of the end use of biomass that is imported, they are both defined in terms of the amount of biomass that could in the future be imported for a specific cost.

Note that the methodology as applied for producing the estimates is detailed in S2BIOM report D1.6: Spatial data base on sustainable biomass cost-supply of lignocellulosic biomass in Europe. Content, methods & data sources.

2.7.2 Cost and supply potential

The final cost supply curves were estimated for 2010, 2020, and 2030. In term of the cost supply curve for bioenergy, the import potential is shown in Figure 60, where the potential is shown in aggregate terms covering both import of wood chips and wood pellets. As shown in Figure 60, the import potential to EU from the rest of the world of wood chips and wood pellets is substantial.

In terms of the cost supply curve for biofuel, the import potential is shown in Figure 61 where the potential is shown for the three main categories of biofuels: 1st generation ethanol from wheat, corn and sugar cane; 2nd generation ethanol from woody biomass; and biodiesel from rape, sunflower, soya and palm oil.

Figure 60: The estimated cost supply curves in 2020 and 2030 for bioenergy. The import potential is defined in terms of import of wood chips and wood pellets [ton dry mass per year], while the price is defined in terms of the cost that a consumer needs to pay for the feedstock [EUR per GJ].

Figure 61: The estimated cost supply curve in 2020 and 2030 for biofuels. The potential is defined in terms of import of specific biofuels [PJ per year], while the price is defined in terms of the cost that a consumer needs to pay for the commodity [EUR per GJ].

3 Literature

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Kton	Straw& stubbles			Prunings			Unused grassland cuttings			Dedicated crops			Agro-industrial residues			Total		
	2012	2020	2030	2012	2020	2030	2012	2020	2030	2012	2020	2030	2012	2020	2030	2012	2020	2030
Kosovo	287	261	279	3	3	3				1,788	1,975	2,056	3	2	2	2,089	2,250	2,349
Moldova	0	0	0	154	154	154				1,303	1,303	1,303	22	23	24	1,499	1,501	1,502
Montenegro	13	8	8	7	7	7				125	131	128	1	1	1	155	157	155
FYROM	254	217	219	31	38	44				815	791	790	31	32	33	1,145	1,093	1,100
Serbia	8,343	5,783	5,814	155	169	169				1,407	1,723	1,653	247	235	241	10,217	7,977	7,945
Turkey	39,482	25,024	26,724	1,060	1,108	1,093				17,813	19,127	18,395	4,540	4,402	4,527	63,148	49,921	51,003
Ukraine	43,170	43,170	43,170	250	0	0				14,910	14,910	14,910	2,945	2,945	2,945	61,510	61,267	61,271
Non EU countries	91,249	74,193	75,927	1,495	1,316	1,306				34,944	36,552	35,748	7,763	7,613	7,745	136,020	120,258	121,320
EU 28 & Non EU countries	331,328	237,669	232,611	6,217	5,790	5,789				86,676	134,414	143,262	37,453	37,541	38,936	525,162	479,034	484,300

Kton	2012						2020						2030					
	Rice	Cereal	OSR	Grain maize stover	Sugarbeet leaves & tops	Sunflower	Rice	Cereal	OSR	Grain maize stover	Sugarbeet leaves & tops	Sunflower	Rice	Cereal	OSR	Grain maize stover	Sugarbeet leaves & tops	Sunflower
Serbia	-	1,457	21	3,716	2,716	434	-	1,420	30	3,611	270	451	-	1,557	50	3,518	264	425
Turkey	505	23,707	106	2,116	11,670	1,377	627	19,845	154	2,259	944	1,194	613	21,489	149	2,495	881	1,097
Ukraine	9	13,743	644	10,470	5,299	13,005	9	13,743	644	10,470	5,299	13,005	9	13,743	644	10,470	5,299	13,005
Non EU countries	526	39,092	773	16,349	19,690	14,820	646	35,171	829	16,381	6,514	14,653	631	36,953	845	16,521	6,445	14,531
EU 28 & Non EU countries	2,963	151,756	13,532	43,413	97,905	21,758	2,726	141,102	12,697	45,896	12,274	22,973	2,647	137,483	11,899	45,094	12,461	23,027

Table 10 Total biomass from prunings in permanent crops in EU and neighbour countries [Kton dm] for the Base (BP) in 2012, 2020 and 2030

Kton	2012				2020				2030			
	Vineyards	Seed and soft fruit	Olives	Citrus	Vineyards	Seed and soft fruit	Olives	Citrus	Vineyards	Seed and soft fruit	Olives	Citrus
Austria	18	15	-	-	39	15	-	-	36	15	-	-
Belgium	-	38	-	-	-	32	-	-	-	33	-	-
Bulgaria	0	13	-	-	0	7	-	-	0	8	-	-
Cyprus	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	6
Czech Republic	-	35	-	-	-	32	-	-	-	31	-	-
Germany	10	85	-	-	67	82	-	-	66	78	-	-
Denmark	-	1	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	1	-	-
Estonia	-	0	-	-	-	0	-	-	-	0	-	-
Greece	10	105	70	18	5	102	77	14	3	109	91	14
Spain	11	153	2,338	132	16	129	2,207	123	13	113	2,250	131
Finland	-	1	-	-	-	2	-	-	-	2	-	-
France	31	130	0	0	52	98	1	0	52	72	1	0
Croatia	9	16	5	5	9	19	4	4	8	20	4	4
Hungary	0	142	-	-	0	131	-	-	0	134	-	-
Ireland	-	0	-	-	-	0	-	-	-	0	-	-
Italy	119	175	223	15	72	177	214	11	69	146	220	11
Lithuania	-	0	-	-	-	0	-	-	-	0	-	-
Luxembourg	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Latvia	-	0	-	-	-	0	-	-	-	0	-	-
Malta	0	0	0	0	0	0	-	0	0	0	-	-
Netherlands	0	31	-	-	-	27	-	-	-	23	-	-
Poland	0	577	-	-	-	549	-	-	-	593	-	-
Portugal	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Romania	5	136	-	-	3	110	-	-	2	88	-	-
Sweden	-	4	-	-	-	3	-	-	-	2	-	-
Slovenia	0	3	0	-	0	3	0	-	0	3	0	-
Slovakia	0	11	-	-	0	13	-	-	0	12	-	-
United kingdom	-	26	-	-	-	21	-	-	-	18	-	-
EU 28	215	1,697	2,636	174	263	1,551	2,503	157	249	1,501	2,566	167
Albania	3	27	9	0	4	37	8	0	4	51	8	0
Bosnia and Herzegovina	2	67	-	0	3	85	-	0	3	105	-	0
Kosovo	0	3	-	-	0	3	-	-	0	3	-	-
Moldova	32	123	-	-	32	123	-	-	32	123	-	-
Montenegro	1	6	0	0	1	6	0	0	1	6	0	0
FYROM	6	24	1	-	5	33	1	-	4	39	1	-

Kton	2012				2020				2030			
	Vineyards	Seed and soft fruit	Olives	Citrus	Vineyards	Seed and soft fruit	Olives	Citrus	Vineyards	Seed and soft fruit	Olives	Citrus
Serbia	13	142	-	-	15	154	-	-	13	156	-	-
Turkey	179	667	206	7	152	779	172	6	125	767	197	3
Ukraine	16	233	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Non EU countries	214	1,066	207	7	171	966	173	6	142	963	198	3
EU 28 & Non EU countries	429	2,763	2,843	182	434	2,518	2,676	163	392	2,463	2,764	170

Table 12 Total biomass from straw & stubbles in EU and neighbour countries [Kton dm] for the Technical, Base (BP) and User defined (UD) potentials in 2012, 2020 and 2030

Kton	Technical potential			Base potential			UD potential		
	2012	2020	2030	2012	2020	2030	2012	2020	2030
Austria	6,603	3,525	3,595	5,384	2,843	2,894	5,149	2,620	2,677
Belgium	6,645	2,179	2,127	6,556	2,037	2,094	6,081	1,635	1,664
Bulgaria	7,761	8,218	8,157	6,171	6,660	6,396	5,994	6,555	6,252
Cyprus	66	62	61	0	0	0	-	-	-
Czech Republic	11,015	7,818	7,726	10,039	7,210	7,112	9,831	7,031	6,953
Germany	59,509	38,240	35,507	45,727	28,038	26,482	43,567	25,981	24,474
Denmark	9,741	6,970	6,650	2,027	1,516	1,483	1,271	799	763
Estonia	857	841	976	0	0	0	0	0	0
Greece	4,370	3,877	4,226	2,340	1,825	2,073	1,958	1,483	1,712
Spain	23,107	19,479	19,974	14,792	11,949	12,161	12,706	9,990	10,151
Finland	3,644	3,439	3,581	1,603	1,604	1,700	1,447	1,459	1,555
France	78,415	54,833	53,044	59,154	36,864	35,573	56,181	33,969	32,663
Croatia	3,813	2,558	2,495	3,107	2,084	2,033	2,980	1,957	1,896
Hungary	12,635	12,160	11,741	10,278	9,927	9,571	10,080	9,762	9,415
Ireland	1,638	1,561	1,566	0	0	0	0	0	0
Italy	18,961	14,661	14,968	8,391	6,747	6,760	7,536	5,872	5,909
Lithuania	3,808	3,136	3,022	532	477	457	424	371	348
Luxembourg	160	143	127	156	140	124	130	114	100
Latvia	1,592	1,863	1,821	202	234	234	143	183	182
Malta	8	11	9	0	0	0	-	-	-
Netherlands	6,642	1,531	1,563	5,250	1,097	1,147	4,891	725	776
Poland	34,922	24,185	20,950	29,325	20,360	17,503	28,256	19,349	16,492
Portugal	979	852	959	324	272	336	212	204	242
Romania	17,349	16,187	16,103	12,460	11,726	11,018	11,906	11,148	10,604
Sweden	5,971	3,624	3,452	3,849	2,283	2,108	3,621	2,070	1,904
Slovenia	452	489	446	0	0	0	0	0	0
Slovakia	3,916	3,128	2,947	2,913	2,140	1,995	2,864	2,104	1,956
United kingdom	24,185	16,663	18,101	9,500	5,443	5,431	8,652	4,659	4,668
EU 28	348,764	252,234	245,893	240,079	163,476	156,684	225,883	150,040	143,356
				-	-	-	-	-	-
Albania	657	485	518	314	232	247	149	95	93
Bosnia and Herzegovina	873	849	817	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kosovo	352	321	343	287	261	279	238	220	236
Moldova	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Montenegro	17	11	12	13	8	8	7	5	5
FYROM	532	455	458	254	217	219	191	155	155
Serbia	10,239	7,097	7,136	8,343	5,783	5,814	8,000	5,493	5,556
Turkey	60,475	38,329	40,933	39,482	25,024	26,724	37,282	22,940	24,412
Ukraine	69,852	69,852	69,852	43,170	43,170	43,170	42,511	42,511	42,511
Non EU countries	142,997	117,398	120,068	91,862	74,694	76,462	88,378	71,418	72,968
				-	-	-	-	-	-
EU 28 & Non EU countries	491,762	369,632	365,961	331,941	238,170	233,146	314,262	221,458	216,323

Table 13 Total biomass from prunings from permanent crops in EU and neighbour countries [Kton dm] for the Technical, Base (BP) and User defined (UD) potentials in 2012, 2020 and 2030

Kton	Technical potential			Base potential		
	2012	2020	2030	2012	2020	2030
Austria	45	58	56	33	54	51
Belgium	38	32	33	38	32	33
Bulgaria	148	117	112	13	7	8
Cyprus	67	67	72	4	5	6
Czech Republic	36	32	31	35	32	31
Germany	106	168	162	95	149	144
Denmark	5	4	4	1	1	1
Estonia	4	2	1	0	0	0
Greece	1,507	1,543	1,637	204	199	216
Spain	5,428	4,874	4,984	2,634	2,475	2,507
Finland	4	5	5	1	2	2
France	1,120	1,036	993	162	151	126
Croatia	116	110	114	34	35	37
Hungary	263	231	227	142	131	134
Ireland	2	2	1	0	0	0
Italy	3,171	2,760	2,695	532	473	446
Lithuania	23	11	8	0	0	0
Luxembourg	0	0	0	0	0	0
Latvia	11	5	2	0	0	0
Malta	4	2	2	0	0	0
Netherlands	31	27	23	31	27	23
Poland	609	577	621	577	549	593
Portugal	835	670	763	2	0	0
Romania	442	333	279	141	113	89
Sweden	4	3	3	4	3	2
Slovenia	30	30	26	3	3	3
Slovakia	24	20	18	11	13	12
United kingdom	36	33	31	26	21	18
EU 28	14,107	12,752	12,901	4,722	4,474	4,483
Albania	95	114	136	38	49	64
Bosnia and Herzegovina	113	142	170	69	88	109
Kosovo	5	5	5	3	3	3
Moldova	335	335	335	154	154	154
Montenegro	16	16	17	7	7	7
FYROM	60	69	77	31	38	44
Serbia	305	323	323	155	169	169
Turkey	2,742	2,762	2,783	1,060	1,108	1,093
Ukraine	400	0	0	250	0	0
Non EU countries	4,071	3,765	3,845	1,767	1,617	1,644
EU 28 & Non EU countries	18,178	16,518	16,746	6,489	6,091	6,126

A3 Other land use

Table 21 Residues from road side verge grass in EU and neighbouring countries [1000 t]

Kton	Road side verges		
	2012	2020	2030
Austria	93	96	97
Belgium	101	103	105
Bulgaria	79	81	83
Cyprus	5	5	5
Czech Republic	75	77	78
Germany	686	704	716
Denmark	69	71	72
Estonia	21	22	22
Greece	100	102	104
Spain	343	352	358
Finland	138	142	144
France	724	743	756
Croatia	48	49	50
Hungary	81	83	85
Ireland	46	47	48
Italy	392	402	409
Lithuania	44	45	46
Luxembourg	7	7	8
Latvia	38	39	39
Malta	0	0	0
Netherlands	121	124	127
Poland	242	248	252
Portugal	83	85	86
Romania	127	130	132
Sweden	179	184	187
Slovenia	20	21	21
Slovakia	58	60	61
United kingdom	375	385	391
EU 28	4,294	4,410	4,483
Albania	10	10	10
Bosnia and Herzegovina	32	33	33
Kosovo	8	8	8
Macedonia	15	15	15
Moldova	20	21	21
Montenegro	9	9	10
FYROM	94	96	98
Serbia	65	67	68
Turkey	253	260	264
Ukraine	235	242	246
Non EU countries	647	665	676
EU 28 & Non EU countries	4,941	5,075	5,159

Table 26 Secondary Residues from Other Wood Processing Industries in EU and neighbour countries [1000 t]

Country	2012			2020			2030		
	BP	UP1	UP2	BP	UP1	UP2	BP	UP1	UP2
Austria	645	645	89	631	631	92	630	630	97
Belgium	226	226	22	200	200	20	193	193	20
Bulgaria	164	164	22	170	170	21	177	177	23
Cyprus	38	38	0	47	47	0	50	50	0
Czech Republic	554	554	81	610	610	91	629	629	95
Germany	2886	2886	125	2877	2877	128	2973	2973	137
Denmark	234	234	34	239	239	29	182	182	13
Estonia	238	238	42	252	252	45	269	269	51
Greece	155	155	10	181	181	8	194	194	7
Spain	1178	1178	141	1218	1218	153	1203	1203	158
Finland	668	668	415	617	617	383	649	649	412
France	1259	1259	119	1245	1245	122	1414	1414	130
Croatia	71	71	9	87	87	13	108	108	16
Hungary	328	328	29	469	469	42	573	573	56
Ireland	69	69	0	74	74	0	78	78	0
Italy	2206	2206	204	1651	1651	169	1715	1715	174
Lithuania	384	384	40	431	431	45	506	506	57
Luxembourg	27	27	0	24	24	0	24	24	0
Latvia	266	266	98	401	401	166	463	463	188
Malta	9	9	0	9	9	0	9	9	0
Netherlands	334	334	0	338	338	0	349	349	0
Poland	2357	2357	183	3158	3158	206	3420	3420	219
Portugal	531	531	31	473	473	28	466	466	29
Romania	1066	1066	243	1693	1693	400	1905	1905	463
Sweden	413	413	34	560	560	56	608	608	64
Slovenia	169	169	38	238	238	53	296	296	65
Slovakia	199	199	16	216	216	18	241	241	22
United kingdom	1469	1469	0	1463	1463	0	1543	1543	0
EU 28	18142	18142	2024	19572	19572	2289	20866	20866	2496
Albania	23	23	0	24	24	0	27	27	0
Bosnia and Herzegovina	89	89	11	92	92	11	97	97	12
Kosovo	9	9	0	10	10	0	11	11	0
Moldova	74	74	0	77	77	0	89	89	0
Montenegro	12	12	1	12	12	1	14	14	1
FYROM	16	16	0	17	17	0	19	19	0
Serbia	88	88	15	92	92	16	104	104	17
Turkey	1428	1428	76	1575	1575	84	1693	1693	91
Ukraine	342	342	101	456	456	141	508	508	155
Non EU countries	2079	2079	204	2354	2354	254	2561	2561	277
EU 28 & Non EU countries	20222	20222	2228	21926	21926	2543	23427	23427	2774

Table 27 Secondary Residues from Other Wood Processing Industries in EU and neighbour countries [1000 m³]

Country	2012			2020			2030		
	BP	UP1	UP2	BP	UP1	UP2	BP	UP1	UP2
Austria	1295	1295	198	1270	1270	205	1271	1271	217
Belgium	450	450	48	399	399	44	386	386	44
Bulgaria	317	317	48	326	326	47	340	340	51
Cyprus	78	78	0	95	95	0	102	102	0
Czech Republic	1076	1076	182	1184	1184	204	1222	1222	213
Germany	5743	5743	278	5728	5728	286	5925	5925	306
Denmark	467	467	75	476	476	64	359	359	30
Estonia	485	485	93	515	515	101	549	549	113
Greece	301	301	21	351	351	17	375	375	16
Spain	2343	2343	316	2424	2424	341	2397	2397	352
Finland	1436	1436	927	1327	1327	855	1397	1397	920
France	2548	2548	265	2522	2522	273	2862	2862	290
Croatia	135	135	20	164	164	28	205	205	35
Hungary	650	650	65	930	930	95	1137	1137	125
Ireland	142	142	0	153	153	0	160	160	0
Italy	4310	4310	455	3232	3232	376	3357	3357	389
Lithuania	746	746	90	838	838	101	985	985	128
Luxembourg	59	59	0	54	54	0	53	53	0
Latvia	554	554	218	840	840	370	969	969	419
Malta	16	16	0	16	16	0	16	16	0
Netherlands	649	649	0	656	656	0	678	678	0
Poland	4590	4590	408	6123	6123	461	6626	6626	489
Portugal	1031	1031	70	919	919	63	906	906	64
Romania	2091	2091	542	3327	3327	893	3750	3750	1035
Sweden	830	830	76	1128	1128	126	1225	1225	142
Slovenia	341	341	86	480	480	117	597	597	145
Slovakia	382	382	36	415	415	41	464	464	50
United kingdom	2854	2854	0	2844	2844	0	2999	2999	0
EU 28	35919	35919	4517	38735	38735	5109	41312	41312	5572
Albania	40	40	1	42	42	1	48	48	1
Bosnia and Herzegovina	167	167	24	172	172	25	181	181	27
Kosovo	17	17	1	17	17	1	20	20	1
Moldova	139	139	0	146	146	0	167	167	0
Montenegro	21	21	3	22	22	3	25	25	3
FYROM	29	29	1	31	31	1	35	35	1
Serbia	168	168	34	177	177	35	199	199	38
Turkey	2772	2772	169	3058	3058	187	3288	3288	202
Ukraine	721	721	225	963	963	315	1074	1074	347
Non EU countries	4076	4076	456	4629	4629	567	5039	5039	619
EU 28 & Non EU countries	39994	39994	4973	43364	43364	5676	46350	46350	6191

Table 28 Secondary Residues from Pulp & Paper Industry in EU and neighbour countries [1000 t]

Country	2012			2020			2030		
	BP	UP1	UP2	BP	UP1	UP2	BP	UP1	UP2
Austria	1496	1496	0	1465	1465	0	1465	1465	0
Belgium	321	321	0	319	319	0	319	319	0
Bulgaria	150	150	0	149	149	0	149	149	0
Cyprus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Czech Republic	692	692	0	688	688	0	688	688	0
Germany	1921	1921	0	1939	1939	0	1939	1939	0
Denmark	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Estonia	100	100	0	98	98	0	98	98	0
Greece	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Spain	2140	2140	0	2129	2129	0	2129	2129	0
Finland	8145	8145	0	8518	8518	0	8518	8518	0
France	1462	1462	0	1453	1453	0	1453	1453	0
Croatia	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hungary	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ireland	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Italy	60	60	0	59	59	0	59	59	0
Lithuania	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Luxembourg	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Latvia	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Malta	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Netherlands	4	4	0	4	4	0	4	4	0
Poland	1032	1032	0	1026	1026	0	1026	1026	0
Portugal	2764	2764	0	2750	2750	0	2750	2750	0
Romania	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sweden	9318	9318	0	9735	9735	0	9735	9735	0
Slovenia	7	7	0	7	7	0	7	7	0
Slovakia	783	783	0	779	779	0	779	779	0
United kingdom	19	19	0	19	19	0	19	19	0
EU 28	30415	30415	0	31138	31138	0	31138	31138	0
Albania	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bosnia and Herzegovina	87	87	0	86	86	0	86	86	0
Kosovo	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Moldova	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Montenegro	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
FYROM	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Serbia	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Turkey	6	6	0	6	6	0	6	6	0
Ukraine	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Non EU countries	93	93	0	92	92	0	92	92	0
EU 28 & Non EU countries	30508	30508	0	31230	31230	0	31230	31230	0

Table 29 Secondary Residues from Pulp & Paper Industry in EU and neighbour countries [1000 m³]

Country	2012	2012	2012	2020	2020	2020	2030	2030	2030
	BP	UP1	UP2	BP	UP1	UP2	BP	UP1	UP2
Austria	3340	3340	0	3270	3270	0	3270	3270	0
Belgium	717	717	0	712	712	0	712	712	0
Bulgaria	334	334	0	332	332	0	332	332	0
Cyprus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Czech Republic	1544	1544	0	1536	1536	0	1536	1536	0
Germany	4287	4287	0	4328	4328	0	4328	4328	0
Denmark	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0
Estonia	222	222	0	220	220	0	220	220	0
Greece	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Spain	4777	4777	0	4751	4751	0	4751	4751	0
Finland	18181	18181	0	19013	19013	0	19013	19013	0
France	3264	3264	0	3244	3244	0	3244	3244	0
Croatia	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hungary	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ireland	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Italy	134	134	0	131	131	0	131	131	0
Lithuania	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Luxembourg	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Latvia	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Malta	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Netherlands	9	9	0	9	9	0	9	9	0
Poland	2304	2304	0	2291	2291	0	2291	2291	0
Portugal	6170	6170	0	6138	6138	0	6138	6138	0
Romania	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sweden	20798	20798	0	21731	21731	0	21731	21731	0
Slovenia	17	17	0	16	16	0	16	16	0
Slovakia	1748	1748	0	1739	1739	0	1739	1739	0
United kingdom	43	43	0	41	41	0	41	41	0
EU 28	67891	67891	0	69503	69503	0	69503	69503	0
Albania	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bosnia and Herzegovina	194	194	0	193	193	0	193	193	0
Kosovo	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Moldova	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Montenegro	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
FYROM	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Serbia	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Turkey	14	14	0	13	13	0	13	13	0
Ukraine	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Non EU countries	207	207	0	206	206	0	206	206	0
EU 28 & Non EU countries	68098	68098	0	69709	69709	0	69709	69709	0

A 7 Map types & attribute classification

Biomass potentials can be presented in relative or total amounts. Using the base potential for forestry for 2012 as an example, the map series below illustrate the general options to display quantities in maps. Major options are:

- Quantity per land area (Figure 62)
- Quantity per forest area available for wood supply (Figure 63)
- Total per NUSTS3 area (Figure 64)

The standard option in this atlas for maps to present the quantities is the option per land area (Figure 62). This option shows best the regional availability of biomass and the totals are implicitly indicated as well as via coloured size classes. This option also allows for summation of biomass potentials from multiple categories and sectors.

Biomass potentials can also be estimated per unit of area of a land use type. For example, Figure 63 shows forestry potentials per unit of forest area available for wood supply.

The classification of the quantitative attributes can follow different objectives. The upper map of Figure 63 has a legend where quantities are classified as in Figure 62 supporting a direct visual comparison. The lower map of Figure 63 shows a legend that is optimised to enable a better visualisation of the variability within the map. The latter is the standard option used in this atlas.

Supply from Forests [2012]

Base Potential

tonnes/ha

Figure 62 Map of forestry potentials – Base potential 2012 –Quantities per land area

Supply from Forests [2012]

Base Potential

tonnes/ha forest available for wood supply

Supply from Forests [2012]

Base Potential

tonnes/ha forest available for wood supply

Figure 63 Map of forestry potentials – Base potential 2012 – Quantities per forest area available for wood supply, illustrating the effect of different legends.

The biomass density maps (Figure 62, Figure 63) provide information about the spatial distribution of the biomass, which are indicative for the logistical efforts one has to make to collect all the biomass needed. The map of Figure 64 shows the potential in absolute numbers. This representation can be potentially misleading in the interpretation when spatial units differ considerable in size.

Supply from Forests [2012]

Base Potential

1000 tonnes

- 0
- > 0 - 10
- 10 - 20
- 20 - 50
- 50 - 100
- 100 - 200
- 200 - 400
- 400 - 600
- > 600

Figure 64 Map of forestry potentials – Base potential 2012 –Map of totals per NUTS3 area